
The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT213_ALERT_2_C	Atom C3	has ADP max/min Ratio	3.3	oblate
PLAT213_ALERT_2_C	Atom C9	has ADP max/min Ratio	3.3	prolat
PLAT213_ALERT_2_C	Atom C24	has ADP max/min Ratio	3.4	prolat
PLAT213_ALERT_2_C	Atom C49	has ADP max/min Ratio	3.1	oblate
PLAT220_ALERT_2_C	NonSolvent	Resd 1 C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	3.6	Ratio
PLAT341_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds		0.01113	Ang.
PLAT601_ALERT_2_C	Unit Cell Contains Solvent Accessible VOIDS of .		31	Ang**3
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance		3.361	Check
PLAT910_ALERT_3_C	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).		8	Note
PLAT918_ALERT_3_C	Reflection(s) with I(obs) much Smaller I(calc) .		1	Check
PLAT975_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.88Ang From C17		0.56	eA-3
PLAT975_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Resid. Dens. 0.96Ang From O12		0.42	eA-3

● **Alert level G**

PLAT002_ALERT_2_G	Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite		4	Note
PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms		5	Report
PLAT083_ALERT_2_G	SHELXL Second Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large		25.81	Why ?
PLAT172_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains DFIX Records		1	Report
PLAT173_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains DANG Records		2	Report
PLAT343_ALERT_2_G	Unusual sp? Angle Range in Main Residue for		C17	Check
PLAT367_ALERT_2_G	Long? C(sp?)-C(sp?) Bond C16 - C17		1.55	Ang.
PLAT367_ALERT_2_G	Long? C(sp?)-C(sp?) Bond C17 - C18		1.54	Ang.
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C2	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C3	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C4	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C5	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C6	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C7	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C9	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C12	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C13	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C16	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C18	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C20	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C21	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C22	(Sohnke SpGr)	S	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C24	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C25	(Sohnke SpGr)	R	Verify
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints		3	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600		23	Note
PLAT961_ALERT_5_G	Dataset Contains no Negative Intensities		Please	Check
PLAT965_ALERT_2_G	The SHELXL WEIGHT Optimisation has not Converged		Please	Check
PLAT967_ALERT_5_G	Note: Two-Theta Cutoff Value in Embedded .res ..		56.0	Degree
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		5	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain

0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully

12 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight

30 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
15 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
5 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
19 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
3 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

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